

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

EARLY BREAST CANCER DETECTION AND DIAGNOSIS IN KAZAKHSTAN USING MACHINE LEARNING METHODS

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Abstract

Breast cancer is a significant public health concern in Kazakhstan, with limited access to screening and diagnostic services, inadequate public awareness, and other socioeconomic factors posing significant challenges to effective early detection and diagnosis. In recent years, efforts have been made to improve early breast cancer detection through national cancer control programs and international partnerships. However, there is still a need for further research and improvement in this area. Machine learning (ML) methods have shown promise in assisting healthcare professionals in detecting and diagnosing breast cancer at an early stage. This paper proposes a comprehensive understanding of the current state of breast cancer screening and diagnosis in Kazakhstan, highlighting areas for further research and improvement. A complex model for detecting breast cancer signs can be developed using ML algorithms, which have the capability to analyze large datasets of medical images and patient information, leading to accurate and prompt diagnoses. With ML algorithms, healthcare professionals can remotely screen patients for breast cancer, reducing the need for in-person visits, and enabling patients to receive personalized and effective treatments, improving patient outcomes and reducing healthcare costs.

Keywords: early breast cancer detection, diagnosis, machine learning, Kazakhstan, medical images, personalized treatment, national cancer control programs, public awareness, socioeconomic barriers.

Introduction

Breast cancer is one of the most prevalent forms of cancer among women worldwide, including Kazakhstan. Early detection of breast cancer is crucial for increasing the chances of successful treatment and improving the overall survival rates of patients. However, in many countries, including Kazakhstan, there are still challenges to achieving effective early detection of breast cancer, including limited access to screening and diagnostic services, inadequate public awareness of the importance of early detection, and other socioeconomic factors.

In recent years, efforts have been made to improve early breast cancer detection in Kazakhstan. The government has implemented national cancer control programs and initiatives aimed at increasing public awareness and promoting early screening and diagnosis. Additionally, partnerships between international organizations and local healthcare providers have been established to improve access to screening and diagnostic services, train healthcare professionals, and enhance overall cancer care.

Despite these efforts, there is still room for improvement in early breast cancer detection. Continued investment in improving access to screening and diag-

nostic services, increasing public awareness and education, and addressing socioeconomic barriers will be critical in reducing the burden of breast cancer and improving outcomes for patients in Kazakhstan.

Resizing images using various of techniques:

When resizing the medical images, it was crucial to lose as little detail as possible because the cancer is frequently small and the images themselves are enormous. That is why it is better to find the way to crop and resize the image and try to save more information as possible so it will be convenient in training part. To save as much information as possible and make the image more useful for the training part, it is therefore essential to determine how to crop and resize the image.

The field of generative modeling, particularly using GANs, requires accurate evaluation metrics to discern which methods are performing better [1]. In visual data, standard metrics like Inception Score, Kernel Inception Distance, and Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) are used to evaluate models by measuring the discrepancy between generated and natural images in a deep feature space [2]. However, seemingly insignificant low-level operations like image processing libraries and image compression can cause significant discrepancies in high-level statistics.

Figure 1. Downsampling circle

In (Fig. 1) an input image is resized by a factor of 8 using different image processing libraries, and the resulting images are compared. The top row shows the Lanczos, bicubic, and bilinear implementations by PIL, which adjust the antialiasing filter width by the downsampling factor. However, other implementations, including those used for PyTorch-FID and TensorFlow-FID, use fixed filter widths, leading to aliasing artifacts that resemble naive nearest subsampling. These artifacts introduce inconsistencies in the calculation of downstream metrics like Fréchet Inception Distance [7], Kernel Inception Distance [4], Inception

Score [2], and Perceptual Path Length [6]. It is worth noting that the antialias flag is available in TensorFlow 2, but it is set to False by default when calculating FID. In (Fig 1.) different image processing libraries like: OpenCV, TensorFlow and PyTorch can produce drastically different results for the same input image, while saving images in JPEG format with default parameters can add quantization and low-level statistical differences. These discrepancies induced by low-level differences can cause variations when used for evaluation protocols, even with the most commonly used FID metric [3, 7, 6, 6, 61].

Figure 2. Interpolation Filters. In this comparison, examination the adaptive filters used by PIL (top) and the non-adaptive filter used by PyTorch (bottom) happens. The PyTorch and TensorFlow implementations of FID use a fixed-width bilinear interpolation that is independent of the resizing ratio. However, Clean-FID proposes a new implementation that follows standard signal processing principles and adapts the filter to prevent aliasing.

The proposed implementation adaptively stretches the filter to ensure that it is appropriate for the specific resizing ratio being used. The horizontal axes represent the spatial coordinates, while the vertical axes represent the kernel intensity.

(Fig. 2) shows that the resizing function used by FID implementations in TensorFlow and PyTorch does not prefilter the image, resulting in aliasing artifacts as shown in (Fig. 1.) Resizing can occur during data preprocessing (training with lower resolution) or at evaluation time (resizing to 299 resolution to compute the FID metric), and in both cases, inconsistent resizing functions can induce downstream variations. Inconsistent resizing during data preprocessing can change the training data distribution, while inconsistencies during evaluation can cause changes in subsequent feature extraction. To address this issue, stronger bicubic filters and adjusting prefiltering width based on resizing factors as guided by signal processing principles are proposed as standardized protocols [9]. Another issue investigated is the effect of image compression, which can corrupt downstream feature extraction and drastically affect performance. Interestingly, when training images are saved with JPEG compression, GANs are unable to fully mimic the induced artifacts, and large FID improvements can be artificially achieved by tweaking JPEG compression ratios when storing generated images [10]. The importance of low-level image processing steps, such as resizing and quantization, when training and evaluating generative models like GANs, is surprising. The experiments focus on the

widely adopted FID metric but also show additional results on the KID [4] metric and IS [2] and Perceptual Path Length [6] metrics in the supplement.

Vision Transformers

The proposed pipeline for breast cancer detection from four multi-view mammograms using Vision Transformers is presented in (Fig. 3). The design is similar to Multi-view Vision Transformer (MVT) used for 3D objects recognition in natural images. The model consists of two major parts, local Transformer blocks and global Transformer blocks [11].

The local Transformer blocks process information from each view image individually, while the global Transformer blocks process information from the four view mammograms jointly. Both local and global Transformer blocks have the same design, including self-attention, multi-head attention, and multi-layer perceptron.

The model's inputs are image patches and position embeddings, which are fed into local Transformer blocks to learn within-mammogram dependencies. The weights of local Transformer blocks are shared among the four mammograms. The outputs of the four mammograms are concatenated and fed into global Transformer blocks to learn inter-mammogram dependencies. Finally, an MLP head is used to classify the case as benign or malignant based on the class token of the last global Transformer block

Figure 3. Vision Transformers pipeline

Conclusion

Overall, with ml algorithms, healthcare professionals can remotely screen patients for breast cancer, reducing the need for in-person visits, and enabling patients to receive personalized and effective treatments, improving patient outcomes and reducing healthcare costs. When resizing medical images for use in ml algorithms, it is crucial to lose as little detail as possible to ensure accurate diagnoses. standard metrics for evaluating ml models on visual data can be affected by seemingly insignificant low-level operations like image processing libraries and image compression, causing significant discrepancies in high-level statistics. Moreover, resizing functions can induce downstream variations during data preprocessing and evaluation, making it important to use consistent and appropriate resizing functions. Further research and investment in breast cancer detection and diagnosis, including the use of ml algorithms, is necessary to improve outcomes for patients in Kazakhstan.

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